

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Journal of Diabetes and Its Complications

journal homepage: WWW.JDCJOURNAL.COM

Prevalence of ECG abnormalities in people with type 2 diabetes: The Hoorn Diabetes Care System cohort

Peter P. Harms^{a,*}, Amber A. van der Heijden^a, Femke Rutters^b, Hanno L. Tan^{c,d}, Joline W.J. Beulens^{b,e}, Giel Nijpels^a, Petra Elders^a, for ESCAPE-NET

^a Amsterdam UMC, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Department of General Practice Medicine, Amsterdam Public Health Research Institute, De Boelelaan 1117, Amsterdam, the Netherlands

^b Amsterdam UMC, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, Amsterdam Public Health Research Institute, De Boelelaan 1117, Amsterdam, the Netherlands

^c Amsterdam UMC, University of Amsterdam, Heart Center, Department of Experimental and Clinical Cardiology, Amsterdam Cardiovascular Sciences Research Institute, Meibergdreef 9, Amsterdam, the Netherlands

^d Netherlands Heart Institute, Utrecht, the Netherlands

^e Julius Center for Health Sciences and Primary Care, University Medical Center Utrecht, Utrecht, the Netherlands

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 13 August 2020

Received in revised form 26 October 2020

Accepted 1 November 2020

Available online xxxxx

Keywords:

Cardiovascular

Cardiovascular disease

CVD

Diabetes

ECG

Electrocardiogram

Hypertension

Prevalence

Risk factors

ABSTRACT

Aims: The American Diabetes Association, and the joint European Society of Cardiology and European Association for the Study of Diabetes guidelines recommend a resting ECG in people with type 2 diabetes with hypertension or suspected cardiovascular disease (CVD). However, knowledge on the prevalence of ECG abnormalities is incomplete. We aimed to analyse the prevalence of ECG abnormalities and their cross-sectional associations with cardiovascular risk factors in people with type 2 diabetes.

Methods: We used data of the Diabetes Care System cohort obtained in 2018. ECG abnormalities were defined using the Minnesota Classification and categorised into types of abnormalities. The prevalence was calculated for the total population ($n = 8068$) and the subgroup of people without a history of CVD ($n = 6494$). Logistic regression models were used to assess cross-sectional associations.

Results: Approximately one-third of the total population had minor (16.0%) or major (13.1%) ECG abnormalities. Of the participants without a CVD history, approximately one-quarter had minor (14.9%) or major (9.1%) ECG abnormalities, and for those with hypertension or very high CVD risk, the prevalence was 27.5% and 39.6%, respectively. ECG abnormalities were significantly and consistently associated with established CVD risk factors.

Conclusions: Resting ECG abnormalities are common in all people with type 2 diabetes (29.1%), including those without a history of CVD (24.0%), and their prevalence is related to traditional cardiovascular risk factors such as older age, male sex, hypertension, lower HDL cholesterol, higher BMI, and smoking behaviour.

© 2020 The Authors. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

People with type 2 diabetes have a two-fold higher risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD) compared to the general population.^{1–3} In the general population, resting electrocardiogram (ECG) abnormalities, such as pathological Q-waves, bundle branch block, tall R-wave/left ventricular hypertrophy, abnormal QRS-axis and ST-segment abnormalities are

associated with excess risk of CVD morbidity or mortality, independently of known cardiovascular risk factors, and the reported prevalence is normally around a few percent.^{4–12}

Despite its intuitive appeal, the benefit of cardiac screening using ECG has long been questioned.^{13–18} Screening with an ECG must not only reliably identify unrecognized CVD or determine the risk for a future CVD event, but findings must also be prevalent enough. Moreover, they must lead to clinical actions resulting in improvements in clinical outcomes that are superior to those resulting from existing preventative strategies.^{19,20} Both the American Diabetes Association (ADA), and the recent joint European Society of Cardiology and European Association for the Study of Diabetes (ESC/EASD) guidelines recommend to regularly perform a resting ECG in people with type 2 diabetes and hypertension or suspected CVD, without mentioning a time interval.^{21,22}

To date, several studies have reported the prevalence of ECG abnormalities in people with type 2 diabetes. However, these studies present an incomplete picture because they focused on solitary ECG

Abbreviations: ADA, American Diabetes Association; BBB, bundle branch block; BMI, Body Mass Index; CVD, cardiovascular disease; DCS, Diabetes Care System; EASD, European Association for the Study of Diabetes; ECG, electrocardiogram; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; ESC, European Society of Cardiology; GP, general practitioner; GCP, Good Clinical Practice; MC, Minnesota Classification; SCORE, Systematic Coronary Risk Evaluation; T2D, type 2 diabetes; UACR, urinary albumin creatinine ratio.

* Corresponding author at: Amsterdam UMC, Location VUmc, Department of General Practice Medicine, room B-357, Van der Boerhorststraat 7, 1081BT Amsterdam, the Netherlands.

E-mail address: p.p.harms@amsterdamumc.nl (P.P. Harms).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdiacomp.2020.107810>

1056-8727/© 2020 The Authors. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Please cite this article as: P.P. Harms, A.A. van der Heijden, F. Rutters, et al., Prevalence of ECG abnormalities in people with type 2 diabetes: The Hoorn Diabetes Care System cohort..., Journal of Diabetes and Its Complications, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdiacomp.2020.107810>

abnormalities,^{23–28} were conducted in relatively small samples (<500 participants)^{16,28–31} or included only people with Native American or Afro-American ancestry.^{32–34} Furthermore, the reported prevalence of ECG abnormalities varied greatly among these studies, ranging from a few percent up to about 40%, depending on the type of ECG abnormalities specified and study population.

We aimed to analyse the prevalence of resting ECG abnormalities and their cross-sectional associations with cardiovascular risk factors in people with type 2 diabetes.

2. Subjects, materials and methods

2.1. Design and population

The Hoorn Diabetes Care System (DCS) cohort is a prospective cohort of people with type 2 diabetes (~90% European ancestry) from primary care that receive centralized and standardized diabetes care. A detailed description of the DCS cohort has been published elsewhere.³⁵ Briefly, in 1996, the DCS started centrally organized diabetes care for all type 2 diabetes patients of collaborating general practitioner (GP) practices from the West-Friesland region of the Netherlands. The number of collaborating GP practices increased until 2010, when most (98%) of the region's GP practices referred their type 2 diabetes patients to the DCS. The DCS cohort's sole inclusion criterion is (newly) diagnosed type 2 diabetes. In 2013, >95% of people with type 2 diabetes from the catchment region participated in the DCS cohort study, according to GP records. At the DCS centre trained healthcare and research personnel interview and examine the participants annually according to standard operating procedures, including an annual 12-lead resting ECG.

2.2. Study sample

We used the cross-sectional data of the interviews and examinations from the year 2018. In 2018, the DCS cohort consisted of 8678 people with type 2 diabetes. Of these participants, 610 were unable to visit the DCS centre, predominantly because they were not fit enough to travel. Instead, when feasible, a home visit examination was performed which lacked an ECG recording and consequently they were excluded from our analysis. Compared to the people with a recorded ECG they were older and had a more unfavourable clinical profile (Supplementary Table S1).

The remaining 8068 participants (93%) with an ECG were used to calculate the prevalence of ECG abnormalities and the prevalence stratified by sex and age groups as well as to study the associations of minor and major ECG abnormalities with traditional cardiovascular risk factors. In a subgroup analysis, the 6494 study participants (80%) without a history of CVD were used to calculate the prevalence of ECG abnormalities and the prevalence stratified by hypertension and estimated ten year fatal CVD risk categories.

2.3. ECG abnormalities

During the examination a standard 10 s, resting 12-lead ECG was digitally recorded. The ECGs were subsequently evaluated and coded following the Minnesota Classification (MC) coding system by one single trained examiner (a qualified GP with more than 23 years of experience in ECG reading). The exact criteria for Minnesota Classification codes have been elaborately described in the Minnesota code manual for electrocardiographic findings.³⁶ In a random sample of 60 ECGs, our ECG scoring was compared with the coding of two independent cardiologists; this revealed a specific agreement of the different codes between 0.78 (95% CI: 0.71 to 0.84) and 0.97 (95% CI: 0.95 to 0.99) (unpublished data).

MC codes concerning a specific section or type of ECG abnormality were pooled into categories (Supplementary Table S2). Concisely, the QS pattern abnormalities category comprised all abnormal Q-waves.

The QRS-axis deviation category contained leftward shift of the QRS-axis (-30° through -90°). The R-waves category encompassed exceedingly tall amplitude R-waves (i.e., Sokolow-Lyon-criterion or any of the following criteria: >26 mm in V5 or V6; >20 mm in II, III or aVF; >15 mm in I; >12 mm in aVL;). The ST-segment abnormalities category included all downward sloping or depressed ST-segments, and/or T-waves that were flat, negative, or biphasic (negative-positive type only). The atrioventricular conduction defects category encompassed prolonged PR (PQ) intervals in the limb leads (≥ 0.22 s). The ventricular conduction defects category comprised incomplete right bundle branch block (BBB), intraventricular conduction delay, complete right BBB and complete left BBB. The arrhythmias category consisted of atrial fibrillation, atrial flutter, and premature atrial or ventricular contractions.

Next, MC codes were classified as minor or major abnormalities in accordance with consensus between previous studies who categorised abnormalities according to perceived importance and/or severity (Supplementary Table S2). Succinctly, the minor abnormalities category included minor QS pattern abnormalities, minor ST-segment abnormalities, complete right bundle branch block, or premature atrial or ventricular contractions. The major abnormalities category included major QS pattern abnormalities, major ST-segment abnormalities, complete left bundle branch block or intraventricular block, or atrial fibrillation or flutter. When minor and major abnormalities were present simultaneously, participants were classified into the major abnormalities category.

2.4. Other measurements

Sex, date of birth and the date of type 2 diabetes diagnosis were recorded at entry into the DCS cohort, and age or the duration of type 2 diabetes was calculated in years since birth or diagnosis. Anthropometric variables measurements included height, weight from which Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated. Height and weight were measured with participants barefooted and in light clothing. BMI was calculated by dividing body weight in kg by height in meters squared. Systolic and diastolic blood pressures were measured twice (3 min apart) at the upper right arm after 5 min of rest with participants in a seated position, using an automatic oscillometric digital blood pressure device (Welch Allyn ProBP 3400, Skaneateles Falls, New York, USA). The mean of the two values was used as the result of the blood pressure reading.

Overnight fasting blood and first-voided urine samples were collected following standard operating procedures. Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) was established using the turbidimetric inhibition immunoassay for whole haemolysed EDTA-blood and was expressed in both mmol/mol and %. Fasting blood glucose level was determined in fluorinated plasma with the UV test using hexokinase. Total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, and triglycerides levels were measured using standard enzymatic methods. LDL cholesterol was subsequently calculated using the Friedewald formula.³⁷ Cholesterol ratio was determined by dividing the total cholesterol by HDL cholesterol. The creatinine concentration was determined enzymatically in both urine and heparinized blood. The urinary albumin concentration was measured immunoturbidimetrically. All laboratory measurements were performed on a Cobas c501, Roche Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany. The estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was calculated using the Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration (CKD-EPI) creatinine equation.³⁸ The urinary albumin creatinine ratio (UACR) was calculated by dividing albumin in mg/l by creatinine in mmol/l.

Hypertension was defined as elevated blood pressure (systolic >140 mmHg or diastolic >90 mmHg) and/or antihypertensive medication use. Dyslipidaemia included elevated LDL-cholesterol (>2.4 mmol/l) and/or lipid lowering medication use. The eGFR was categorised as: normal or high (eGFR >90 ml/min), mildly decreased (eGFR 60–90 ml/min), moderately decreased (eGFR 30–60 ml/min) or severely decreased (eGFR <30 ml/min). Albuminuria was categorised as: normal to mild (UACR <3 mg/mmol), moderate (UACR 3–30 mg/mmol) or

severe (UACR >30 mg/mmol) according to KDIGO 2012 Workgroup guidelines.³⁹ For the subgroup of people without a history of CVD, the estimated ten-year risk of fatal CVD was calculated and considered low to moderate (<5%), high (5–10%), or very high (>10%) according to the European Society of Cardiology's Systematic Coronary Risk Evaluation (SCORE) model from 2003, which is based on sex, age, systolic blood pressure, total cholesterol, and smoking status.⁴⁰ We used the SCORE model from 2003 because there is evidence that the later Dutch re-calibrated version underestimates the actual risk in the general population.⁴¹ For the SCORE calculation of people with hypertension or dyslipidaemia, we used in-treatment levels of systolic blood pressure and total cholesterol.

Medication use, educational level, smoking behaviour, and CVD events were obtained through self-report. Information on medication use was obtained by inspecting dispensing labels and included the name of the drug, prescribed quantity, and dosage, and the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification code. The use of glucose-lowering medication was classified as: no medication, only oral medication, only insulin use, and oral and insulin use. Highest achieved education was classified as either low, middle, or high. Smoking behaviour was classified into three categories: never, a former smoker, and a current smoker. History of CVD was defined as self-reported myocardial infarction, angina pectoris, heart failure, stroke, cardiac arrest, or (ventricular) heart rhythm disorder. An analysis in 453 participants, verifying the self-reported CVD events against regional hospital and GP records, showed the sensitivity of self-report was 86%, and the specificity was 90%, while the positive and negative predictive values were 90% and 87%, respectively.³⁵

2.5. Statistical analyses

Differences between people with or without a recorded ECG, and between people with or without ECG abnormalities were compared for demographic and clinical characteristics, using unpaired Student's *t*-tests, Mann-Whitney *U* tests or a Chi-square tests as appropriate. Because the proportion of missing values for covariates did not exceed the a priori chosen limit of 5% (<0.3% for all covariates, except educational level (2.2%), fasting glucose (2.4%), and urinary albumin (5.0%)), no multiple imputation was performed and instead missing values were excluded pairwise.

The prevalence of minor and major ECG abnormalities, and specific types of ECG abnormalities (i.e., QS pattern, QRS-axis, R-waves, ST-segment, atrioventricular conduction, ventricular conduction, and arrhythmias) was determined for the total study population and the subgroup of people without a history of CVD. Furthermore, for the total study population, the prevalence was stratified by sex and five-year age strata. In the subgroup of people without a history of CVD, the prevalence was stratified by hypertension and estimated ten-year fatal CVD risk strata. The prevalence was computed with a 95% confidence interval (CI) and was checked for trends with increasing age or estimated CVD risk, using linear-by-linear chi-square test.

Univariable and multivariable binary logistic regression models were used to explore the association of cardiovascular risk factors with minor, major, and both minor and major ECG abnormalities, computing odds ratios (ORs) with 95% CIs. The following variables were entered into the models: age, sex, type 2 diabetes duration, educational level, smoking behaviour, BMI, HbA1c, fasting glucose, HDL cholesterol, glucose-lowering medication use, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and categorised eGFR. The multivariable models included all variables simultaneously. The assumptions of binary logistic regression were checked. To compare participants with minor or major ECG abnormalities, respectively, solely to participants without any ECG abnormalities, participants with major ECG abnormalities were excluded from the control group in the minor ECG abnormalities model and vice versa.

For all statistical tests significance was set at the $p < 0.05$ level (two-tailed). All statistical analyses were performed with SPSS version 24 (IBM corporation) for Windows.

3. Results

3.1. Study population characteristics

Table 1 shows the characteristics of the participants. Compared to those without ECG abnormalities, participants with ECG abnormalities were older, more often men, had longer T2D duration and a generally more unfavourable clinical profile.

3.2. Prevalence for the total study population

3.2.1. Total study population, men, and women

Approximately one-third of the study population had minor (16.0%) or major (13.1%) ECG abnormalities (Fig. 1a). Ventricular conduction defects (13.9%) and arrhythmias (11.0%) were the most common specific types of ECG abnormalities in all groups (total, women and men). The prevalence was significantly higher in men compared to women for minor or major abnormalities, QS pattern, QRS-axis, atrioventricular conduction, and ventricular conduction abnormalities.

3.2.2. Stratified by age groups

All ECG abnormalities were more prevalent in older people (Fig. 1b). Between the groups aged below 60 and above 80, the prevalence of minor and major ECG abnormalities increased 15.6%-points and 21.3%-points, respectively. Of the specific types of ECG abnormalities, increase was most marked in the atrioventricular conduction, ventricular conduction and arrhythmia categories. For all abnormalities, clear linear trends for age were detected ($p_{\text{trend-values}} < 0.01$).

3.3. Prevalence for subgroup without CVD

3.3.1. Total subgroup, and those with or without hypertension

Of the participants without a CVD history, approximately one-quarter had minor (14.9%) or major (9.1%) ECG abnormalities (Fig. 2a). Of the specific types of abnormalities, ventricular conduction defects and arrhythmias were the most prevalent. The prevalence was significantly higher in people with hypertension compared to people without hypertension for minor or major abnormalities, QS pattern, R-waves, ST-segment, atrioventricular or ventricular conduction abnormalities, and arrhythmias.

3.3.2. Stratified by estimated CVD risk groups

All ECG abnormalities were more prevalent in people with a higher estimated risk of CVD (Fig. 2b). Between the low to moderate and very high CVD risk groups, the prevalence of minor and major ECG abnormalities increased 13.7%-points and 9.8%-points, respectively. Of the specific types of ECG abnormalities increase was most marked in the atrioventricular conduction, ventricular conduction and arrhythmia categories, respectively. For all abnormalities, clear linear trends for CVD risk were detected ($p_{\text{trend-values}} < 0.01$).

3.4. Cross-sectional associations

In the total population, older age, male sex, smoking behaviour, higher BMI, higher HbA1c, lower fasting glucose, lower HDL cholesterol, hypertension, and moderately decreased eGFR were significantly associated with minor and/or major ECG abnormalities in the multivariable analyses (Table 2). Moreover, older age, male sex, higher BMI, lower HDL cholesterol and hypertension were consistently associated with minor and major ECG abnormalities in all multivariable analyses, independently of other traditional cardiovascular risk factors.

Table 1
Characteristics of the study population stratified by no, minor, or major ECG abnormalities.

Characteristic	Total N = 8068	No ECG abnormalities N = 5723	Minor ECG abnormalities N = 1292	Major ECG abnormalities N = 1053	No vs minor p-value	No vs major p-value
Age (years)	67.7 ± 11.0	65.8 ± 11.0	71.4 ± 9.6	73.4 ± 9.4	<0.01	<0.01
Men (%)	55.6%	52.6%	60.1%	66.4%	<0.01	<0.01
T2D duration (years)	8.7 (9.7)	8.3 (9.3)	9.7 (9.9)	9.7 (10.0)	<0.01	<0.01
T2D duration >10 years (%)	42.4%	39.8%	48.8%	48.9%	<0.01	<0.01
Educational level (%)					0.23	0.09
Low	39.6%	38.9%	40.4%	42.4%		
Middle	43.4%	44.3%	41.7%	41.0%		
High	16.9%	16.8%	17.9%	16.6%		
Smoking behaviour (%)					<0.01	<0.01
Never	31.8%	33.8%	27.2%	27.1%		
Former	53.5%	51.0%	58.2%	61.3%		
Current	14.7%	15.2%	14.6%	11.6%		
BMI (kg/m ²)	30.0 ± 5.4	30.0 ± 5.4	30.0 ± 5.4	29.7 ± 5.4	0.97	0.1
SBP (mmHg)	140.6 ± 20.9	139.1 ± 20.2	144.8 ± 22.0	143.1 ± 21.8	<0.01	<0.01
DBP (mmHg)	78.3 ± 8.5	78.6 ± 8.1	77.6 ± 9.0	77.4 ± 9.8	<0.01	<0.01
HbA1c (mmol/mol)	51.0 (14.0)	50.0 (14.0)	51.0 (15.0)	51.0 (14.0)	0.07	0.31
HbA1c (%)	6.8 (1.3)	6.8 (1.3)	6.8 (1.3)	6.8 (1.3)	0.07	0.31
Fasting glucose (mmol/l)	8.1 (2.3)	8.1 (2.3)	8.2 (2.5)	8.1 (2.2)	0.30	0.74
Total cholesterol (mmol/l)	4.3 ± 1.1	4.4 ± 1.1	4.3 ± 1.1	4.1 ± 1.0	<0.01	<0.01
LDL cholesterol (mmol/l)	2.3 ± 0.9	2.3 ± 0.9	2.2 ± 0.9	2.1 ± 0.9	<0.01	<0.01
HDL cholesterol (mmol/l)	1.3 ± 0.4	1.3 ± 0.4	1.2 ± 0.4	1.2 ± 0.4	<0.01	<0.01
TC/HDL ratio	3.4 (1.5)	3.4 (1.5)	3.4 (1.5)	3.4 (1.6)	0.84	0.34
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	1.6 (1.0)	1.6 (1.0)	1.6 (1.0)	1.5 (1.0)	0.02	0.15
eGFR (ml/min)	74.0 ± 19.7	76.5 ± 19.3	69.7 ± 19.4	65.3 ± 19.1	<0.01	<0.01
UACR (mg/mmol)	0.7 (1.4)	0.6 (1.0)	0.9 (2.4)	1.1 (3.1)	<0.01	<0.01
Glucose-lowering medication use (%)					0.04	<0.01
No medication	22.0%	22.8%	19.7%	20.0%		
Oral only	55.7%	55.9%	56.2%	53.8%		
Insulin only	4.9%	4.6%	5.5%	5.8%		
Oral & insulin	17.5%	16.7%	18.6%	20.4%		
Antihypertensive medication (%)	70.2%	65.0%	78.5%	88.5%	<0.01	<0.01
Lipid-lowering medication (%)	66.4%	64.2%	72.7%	70.4%	<0.01	<0.01
Hypertension (%)	80.1%	75.7%	87.8%	94.2%	<0.01	<0.01
Dyslipidaemia (%)	90.1%	89.7%	91.1%	90.8%	0.14	0.30
eGFR categories (%)					<0.01	<0.01
Normal or high (>90)	21.4%	25.2%	14.7%	9.0%		
Mildly decreased (60–90)	54.8%	55.2%	55.6%	51.7%		
Moderately decreased (30–60)	22.1%	18.4%	26.7%	36.6%		
Severely decreased (<30)	1.6%	1.1%	3.0%	2.7%		
Albuminuria (%)					<0.01	<0.01
Normal to mild (UACR <3)	81.6%	85.1%	75.1%	71.0%		
Moderate (UACR 3–30)	15.4%	12.8%	20.7%	23.3%		
Severe (UACR >30)	2.9%	2.1%	4.2%	5.8%		
History of CVD (%)	19.5%	13.8%	25.2%	43.7%	<0.01	<0.01

Data are presented as mean ± SD, median (IQR), or proportion (%).

T2D, type 2 diabetes; BMI, body mass index; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; HbA1c, haemoglobin A1c; LDL, low density lipoprotein; HDL, high density lipoprotein; TC, total cholesterol; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; UACR, urinary albumin creatinine ratio; CVD, Cardiovascular disease.

In 354 participants, minor and major abnormalities were present simultaneously, these participants were classified into the major category.

4. Discussion

The scarce previous studies in people with type 2 diabetes reported a prevalence of minor or major ECG abnormalities ranging from 12.5% to 37.0%, and from 7.5% to 23%, respectively.^{32,34} However, these results were observed in populations of people with Native American or Afro-American ancestry that may not be applicable to our study population of people with mainly European ancestry. In a sample (n = 100) from a perhaps more comparable population of Indian people with type 2 diabetes without symptomatic CVD, 26.0% had any ECG abnormality.²⁹ In another small sample (n = 221) of Spanish people with type 2 diabetes without known CVD, 24.9% had any ECG abnormality based on the MC.¹⁶ These percentages are equivalent to the 24.0% of minor and major ECG abnormalities we observed in people with type 2 diabetes without a CVD history.

Moreover, a small study from Sub-Saharan Africa compared various specific types of ECG abnormalities in people with type 2 diabetes and also found conduction defects (11.9%) and arrhythmias (16.2%) to be among the most common.³¹ The higher prevalence of

ventricular conduction defects and arrhythmias in people with type 2 diabetes might be related to unrecognized ischemic heart disease and/or contractile dysfunction as a result of impaired Ca²⁺ handling induced by type 2 diabetes, a proposed mechanism of diabetic cardiomyopathy.^{42,43}

The higher prevalence of ECG abnormalities in men and with higher age was previously also shown in the general population.⁴ In addition to age and sex, we found that unfavourable HbA1c, BMI or HDL cholesterol, smoking behaviour, and hypertension were also associated with combined minor and major ECG abnormalities in multivariable-adjusted analyses. Furthermore, in those without a history of CVD, hypertension and (very) high estimated CVD risk was associated with a higher prevalence of all ECG abnormalities.

A potential limitation of this study is that a sole examiner did the coding of ECGs. Nonetheless, the coding is validated by the excellent specific agreement with the judgements of two independent cardiologists, which we reported in paragraph 2.3: 'ECG abnormalities'. Therefore, we do not expect this to influence the results of this study. A second limitation is the exclusion of people without a recorded ECG.

Fig. 1. Prevalence with 95% CI of ECG abnormalities in 2018 for total study population. Panel a: total, women, and men; Panel b: stratified by five-year age groups. QS, QS pattern; QRS, QRS-axis; R, R-waves; ST, ST-segment; AVC, Atrioventricular conduction; VC, Ventricular conduction; AR, Arrhythmias.

Still, comparison of the characteristics with the included people revealed that these people had a more unfavourable clinical profile. Therefore, we expect analyses without this selection bias would have observed even higher prevalence percentages and ORs. A third potential limitation is the SCORE from 2003, since it has been suggested this model underestimates CVD risk in people with type 2 diabetes because diabetes status is not included as a parameter. However, evidence suggests the Dutch re-calibrated SCORE version would exacerbate this underestimation of CVD risk.⁴¹ Additionally, the generalisability to other populations is better for the SCORE from 2003. Therefore, we feel that the SCORE model from 2003 was probably the best option. A fourth potential limitation is the application of the SCORE model to people older than 65 years, and the use of in-treatment levels of systolic blood pressure and total cholesterol in the SCORE calculation of people with hypertension or dyslipidaemia. Nevertheless, in clinical practice and research this is often done to assess the (potential) CVD risk reduction due to treatment effects (pre-post comparison) or to estimate the actual risk of people in treatment. A fifth limitation is the mainly European ancestry of the study population, which limits the applicability of our results to people with different ancestry. A fifth limitation is the cross-

sectional study design which prohibits any inference on causal or temporal relationships of ECG abnormalities with CVD.

Our study has several strengths. First, to our knowledge, it provides the most thorough description of the prevalence of ECG abnormalities in people with type 2 diabetes because it reports on various ECG abnormalities in an unselected and large population with comprehensive measurements. Second, it studies the subgroup of people with type 2 diabetes without a CVD history that is the usual target group for CVD screening with ECG. Third, it considers diverse aspects of ECG abnormality prevalence such as differences across sex, age, hypertension or estimated CVD risk groups, and cross-sectional associations with established cardiovascular risk factors.

Because minor and major ECG abnormalities are relatively common in people with type 2 diabetes, they can potentially be useful in CVD risk screening in people with type 2 diabetes. However, this is only the case if ECG abnormalities are associated with incident CVD events independently of traditional cardiovascular risk factors. If so, ECG abnormalities should also prove to have added prognostic value for CVD morbidity or mortality beyond traditional cardiovascular risk predictors. Future studies should investigate the association of ECG abnormalities with CVD

Fig. 2. Prevalence with 95% CI of ECG abnormalities in 2018 for subgroup without a history of CVD. Panel a: total, people without hypertension (HT), and people with hypertension (HT); Panel b: stratified by ten-year fatal CVD risk estimated with the SCORE model^a (low/moderate: <5%, high: 5–10%, very high: >10%). QS, QS pattern; QRS, QRS-axis; R, R-waves; ST, ST-segment; AVC, Atrioventricular conduction; VC, Ventricular conduction; AR, Arrhythmias. ^a Note that for the SCORE calculation of people with hypertension or dyslipidaemia in-treatment levels of systolic blood pressure and total cholesterol were used.

morbidity or mortality in people with type 2 diabetes, and to what extent they can improve existing CVD prediction models for people with type 2 diabetes. Because the findings presented in this study do not answer these questions, they do not support or disprove the recommendations in the ADA, and the new ESC/EASD diabetes guidelines to screen people with type 2 diabetes and hypertension or suspected CVD using resting ECG. The ADA and ESC/EASD diabetes guidelines are only based on by expert opinion level evidence. Therefore, they need to be further substantiated, preferably with evidence from extensive longitudinal studies in people with type 2 diabetes representative of type 2 diabetes healthcare populations. Interestingly, the prevalence of minor or major ECG abnormalities in people with type 2 diabetes is similar to other populations with an elevated risk of CVD for which added value of ECG abnormalities in screening has been reported: people with hypertension,^{44,45} and older people.¹⁷

5. Conclusion

Resting ECG abnormalities are common in all people with type 2 diabetes (29.1%), including those without a history of CVD (24.0%), and their prevalence is related to traditional cardiovascular risk factors such as older age, male sex, hypertension, lower HDL cholesterol, higher BMI, and smoking behaviour. In line with the ADA and ESC/EASD guidelines resting ECG abnormalities might be a useful tool for CVD screening in people with type 2 diabetes.

Author contributions

Peter P. Harms was involved in conceptualisation, methodology, data curation, formal analysis, writing the original draft, review, and editing. Amber A. van der Heijden was involved in conceptualisation, methodology, data curation, formal analysis, review and editing. Femke Rutters was involved in review, and editing. Hanno L. Tan was involved in review, and editing. Joline W.J. Beulens was involved in conceptualisation, methodology, data curation, formal analysis, review, and editing. Giel Nijpels was involved in conceptualisation, methodology, data curation, formal analysis, review and editing. Petra Elders was involved in conceptualisation, methodology, data curation, formal analysis, review, and editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This study was been made possible by collaboration with the Diabetes Care System West-Friesland. The authors thank participants of this study as well as research staff of the Diabetes Care System West-Friesland.

Table 2

The cross-sectional associations of CVD risk factors with minor, major and both combined ECG abnormalities in people with type 2 diabetes.

Risk factor	OR of minor abnormality		OR of major abnormality		OR of minor or major abnormality	
	N = 7015		N = 6776		N = 8068	
	Univariable	Multivariable	Univariable	Multivariable	Univariable	Multivariable
Age (year)	1.05 (1.05–1.06)**	1.06 (1.05–1.07)**	1.08 (1.07–1.09)**	1.07 (1.06–1.08)**	1.06 (1.06–1.07)**	1.06 (1.06–1.07)**
Men	1.36 (1.20–1.54)**	1.38 (1.19–1.60)**	1.78 (1.55–2.04)**	2.01 (1.70–2.38)**	1.53 (1.39–1.69)**	1.62 (1.44–1.83)**
T2D duration (years)	1.03 (1.02–1.04)**	1.00 (0.99–1.01)	1.03 (1.02–1.04)**	0.99 (0.98–1.01)	1.03 (1.02–1.04)**	1.00 (0.99–1.01)
Educational level						
Low	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
Middle	0.91 (0.79–1.04)	1.06 (0.92–1.22)	0.85 (0.73–0.98)*	1.00 (0.85–1.17)	0.88 (0.79–0.98)*	1.04 (0.92–1.17)
High	1.03 (0.87–1.23)	1.21 (1.00–1.46)	0.91 (0.75–1.10)	1.08 (0.87–1.34)	0.97 (0.85–1.12)	1.15 (0.98–1.34)
Smoking behaviour						
Never	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
Former	1.42 (1.23–1.63)**	1.21 (1.04–1.41)*	1.50 (1.29–1.74)**	1.13 (0.95–1.33)	1.45 (1.30–1.62)**	1.17 (1.04–1.33)**
Current	1.19 (0.98–1.45)	1.48 (1.19–1.83)**	0.95 (0.76–1.19)	1.22 (0.94–1.57)	1.08 (0.93–1.27)	1.35 (1.13–1.62)**
BMI (kg/m ²)	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	1.02 (1.01–1.04)**	0.97 (0.98–1.00)	1.02 (1.01–1.04)*	1.00 (0.99–1.00)	1.02 (1.01–1.03)**
HbA1c (mmol/mol) ^a	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	1.01 (1.00–1.01)	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	1.01 (1.00–1.02)*	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	1.01 (1.00–1.01)*
HbA1c (%) ^a	1.03 (0.98–1.08)	1.07 (0.99–1.17)	1.02 (0.96–1.07)	1.10 (1.01–1.21)*	1.02 (0.98–1.07)	1.09 (1.02–1.16)*
Fasting glucose (mmol/l)	1.01 (0.99–1.04)	0.99 (0.96–1.03)	0.97 (0.95–1.01)	0.95 (0.91–1.00)*	1.00 (0.98–1.02)	0.98 (0.95–1.01)
HDL cholesterol (mmol/l)	0.79 (0.67–0.93)**	0.80 (0.66–0.98)*	0.67 (0.56–0.81)**	0.76 (0.61–0.94)*	0.74 (0.65–0.84)**	0.79 (0.67–0.92)**
Glucose-lowering medication use						
No medication	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
Oral only	1.16 (0.99–1.36)	1.13 (0.95–1.34)	1.09 (0.92–1.30)	1.10 (0.91–1.34)	1.13 (1.00–1.28)	1.12 (0.97–1.30)
Insulin only	1.38 (1.03–1.86)*	1.00 (0.70–1.42)	1.44 (1.05–1.96)*	1.19 (0.81–1.76)	1.41 (1.11–1.78)**	1.09 (0.82–1.46)
Oral & insulin	1.29 (1.06–1.57)*	1.11 (0.86–1.42)	1.40 (1.13–1.72)**	1.24 (0.94–1.64)	1.34 (1.15–1.56)**	1.17 (0.95–1.43)
Hypertension (yes)	2.32 (1.94–2.77)**	1.58 (1.30–1.93)**	5.22 (4.00–6.80)**	2.92 (2.20–3.89)**	3.13 (2.69–3.64)**	1.99 (1.68–2.36)**
Dyslipidaemia (yes)	1.17 (0.95–1.44)	0.96 (0.76–1.20)	1.13 (0.90–1.41)	0.89 (0.69–1.15)	1.15 (0.98–1.36)	0.94 (0.78–1.13)
eGFR categories						
Normal or high (>90)	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference	Reference
Mildly decreased (60–90)	1.73 (1.45–2.05)**	0.95 (0.78–1.17)	2.61 (2.08–3.28)**	1.18 (0.91–1.53)	2.02 (1.75–2.33)**	1.02 (0.86–1.21)
Moderately decreased (30–60)	2.49 (2.05–3.02)**	0.94 (0.74–1.20)	5.53 (4.36–7.02)**	1.56 (1.16–2.09)**	3.51 (2.99–4.11)**	1.16 (0.95–1.42)
Severely decreased (<30)	4.57 (2.99–6.99)**	1.46 (0.90–2.35)	6.53 (4.00–10.64)**	1.45 (0.84–2.52)	5.22 (3.63–7.52)**	1.45 (0.96–2.18)

Data are presented as odds ratios (OR) (95%CI). The multivariable models included all variables simultaneously.

T2D, type 2 diabetes; BMI, body mass index; HbA1c, haemoglobin A1c; HDL, high density lipoprotein; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate.

^a Note that HbA1c is shown in both mmol/mol and % for convenience and HbA1c was not doubly entered into the multivariable models.* Significant at the $p < 0.05$ level.** Significant at the $p < 0.01$ level.

Ethics declaration

The DCS cohort study was approved by the medical ethical review committee of the Amsterdam University Medical Centers, location VUmc, and conducted following the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the Good Clinical Practice (GCP) guidelines for medical research involving humans. All participants of the DCS cohort were informed that anonymized digital records were kept for research purposes and that they could refuse to participate if they did not approve.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the Diabetes Care System (DCS) cohort steering committee but restrictions apply to the availability of these data, which were used under license for the current study, and so are not publicly available. Data are however available from the authors upon reasonable request and with permission of the DCS cohort steering committee.

Funding

This article has been made possible with funding by the Dutch Heart Foundation grant CVON2017-15 RESCUED, the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under acronym ESCAPE-NET (registered under grant agreement No 733381) and Amsterdam University Medical Centers.

The study funders were not involved in the design of the study; the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data; and writing the report. The only restriction imposed was Open Access publication.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdiacomp.2020.107810>.

References

- Emerging Risk Factors C, Sarwar N, Gao P, et al. Diabetes mellitus, fasting blood glucose concentration, and risk of vascular disease: a collaborative meta-analysis of 102 prospective studies. *Lancet* 2010;375:2215–2223 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(10\)60484-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(10)60484-9).
- Woodward M, Zhang X, Barzi F, et al. The effects of diabetes on the risks of major cardiovascular diseases and death in the Asia-Pacific region. *Diabetes Care* 2003;26:360–6.
- Gregg EW, Cheng YJ, Srinivasan M, et al. Trends in cause-specific mortality among adults with and without diagnosed diabetes in the USA: an epidemiological analysis of linked national survey and vital statistics data. *Lancet* 2018;391:2430–40 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)30314-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)30314-3).
- Ashley EA, Raxwal VK, Froelicher VF. The prevalence and prognostic significance of electrocardiographic abnormalities. *Curr Probl Cardiol* 2000;25:1–72.
- Larsen CT, Dahlin J, Blackburn H, et al. Prevalence and prognosis of electrocardiographic left ventricular hypertrophy, ST segment depression and negative T-wave; the Copenhagen City Heart Study. *Eur Heart J* 2002;23:315–24 <https://doi.org/10.1053/euhj.2001.2774>.
- Greenland P, Xie X, Liu K, et al. Impact of minor electrocardiographic ST-segment and/or T-wave abnormalities on cardiovascular mortality during long-term follow-up. *Am J Cardiol* 2003;91:1068–74.
- Rautaharju PM, Prineas RJ, Wood J, Zhang ZM, Crow R, Heiss G. Electrocardiographic predictors of new-onset heart failure in men and in women free of coronary heart disease (from the Atherosclerosis in Communities [ARIC] Study). *Am J Cardiol* 2007;100:1437–41 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjcard.2007.06.036>.
- Rumana N, Turin TC, Miura K, et al. Prognostic value of ST-T abnormalities and left high R waves with cardiovascular mortality in Japanese (24-year follow-up of NIPPON DATA80). *Am J Cardiol* 2011;107:1718–24 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjcard.2011.02.335>.

9. Zhang ZM, Rautaharju PM, Soliman EZ, et al. Mortality risk associated with bundle branch blocks and related repolarization abnormalities (from the Women's Health Initiative [WHI]). *Am J Cardiol* 2012;110:1489-95<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjcard.2012.06.060>.
10. Walsh 3rd JA, Soliman EZ, Ilkhanoff L, et al. Prognostic value of frontal QRS-T angle in patients without clinical evidence of cardiovascular disease (from the Multi-Ethnic Study of Atherosclerosis). *Am J Cardiol* 2013;112:1880-4<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjcard.2013.08.017>.
11. Inohara T, Kohsaka S, Okamura T, et al. Cumulative impact of axial, structural, and repolarization ECG findings on long-term cardiovascular mortality among healthy individuals in Japan: National Integrated Project for Prospective Observation of Non-Communicable Disease and its Trends in the Aged, 1980 and 1990. *Eur J Prev Cardiol* 2014;21:1501-8<https://doi.org/10.1177/2047487313500568>.
12. Rollin A, Maury P, Kee F, et al. Isolated negative T waves in the general population is a powerful predicting factor of cardiac mortality and coronary heart disease. *Int J Cardiol* 2016;203:318-24<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2015.10.118>.
13. Sox Jr HC, Garber AM, Littenberg B. The resting electrocardiogram as a screening test. A clinical analysis. *Ann Intern Med* 1989;111:489-502<https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-111-6-489>.
14. Sox Jr HC, Littenberg B, Garber AM. The role of exercise testing in screening for coronary artery disease. *Ann Intern Med* 1989;110:456-69<https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-110-6-456>.
15. Macfarlane PW, Norrie J, Committee WE. The value of the electrocardiogram in risk assessment in primary prevention: experience from the West of Scotland Coronary Prevention Study. *J Electrocardiol* 2007;40:101-9<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelectrocard.2006.05.003>.
16. de Santiago A, Garcia-Lledo A, Ramos E, Santiago C. Prognostic value of ECGs in patients with type-2 diabetes mellitus without known cardiovascular disease. *Rev Esp Cardiol* 2007;60:1035-41.
17. Auer R, Bauer DC, Marques-Vidal P, et al. Association of major and minor ECG abnormalities with coronary heart disease events. *JAMA* 2012;307:1497-505<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2012.434>.
18. Ohrn AM, Schirmer H, Njolstad I, et al. Electrocardiographic unrecognized myocardial infarction does not improve prediction of cardiovascular events beyond traditional risk factors. The Tromso Study. *Eur J Prev Cardiol* 2018;25:78-86<https://doi.org/10.1177/2047487317736826>.
19. Frame PS, Carlson SJ. A critical review of periodic health screening using specific screening criteria. Part 1: selected diseases of respiratory, cardiovascular, and central nervous systems. *J Fam Pract* 1975;2:29-36.
20. Woolf SH, Battista RN, Anderson GM, Logan AG, Wang E. Assessing the clinical effectiveness of preventive maneuvers: analytic principles and systematic methods in reviewing evidence and developing clinical practice recommendations. A report by the Canadian Task Force on the Periodic Health Examination. *J Clin Epidemiol* 1990;43:891-905[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(90\)90073-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(90)90073-x).
21. American Diabetes A. 10. Cardiovascular disease and risk management: standards of medical care in diabetes-2020. *Diabetes Care* 2020;43:S111-34<https://doi.org/10.2337/dc20-S010>.
22. Cosentino F, Grant PJ, Aboyans V, et al. 2019 ESC Guidelines on diabetes, pre-diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases developed in collaboration with the EASD. *Eur Heart J* 2019<https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehz486>.
23. Valensi P, Lorgis L, Cottin Y. Prevalence, incidence, predictive factors and prognosis of silent myocardial infarction: a review of the literature. *Arch Cardiovasc Dis* 2011;104:178-88<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acvd.2010.11.013>.
24. Davis TM, Coleman RL, Holman RR, Group U. Prognostic significance of silent myocardial infarction in newly diagnosed type 2 diabetes mellitus: United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS) 79. *Circulation* 2013;127:980-7<https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.112.000908>.
25. Cox AJ, Azeem A, Yeboah J, et al. Heart rate-corrected QT interval is an independent predictor of all-cause and cardiovascular mortality in individuals with type 2 diabetes: the Diabetes Heart Study. *Diabetes Care* 2014;37:1454-61<https://doi.org/10.2337/dc13-1257>.
26. Singleton MJ, German C, Hari KJ, et al. QRS duration is associated with all-cause mortality in type 2 diabetes: the diabetes heart study. *J Electrocardiol* 2019;58:150-4<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelectrocard.2019.11.053>.
27. Hadaegh F, Ehteshami-Afshar S, Hajeberahimi MA, Hajsheikholeslami F, Azizi F. Silent coronary artery disease and incidence of cardiovascular and mortality events at different levels of glucose regulation: results of greater than a decade follow-up. *Int J Cardiol* 2015;182:334-9<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2015.01.017>.
28. Dawson A, Morris AD, Struthers AD. The epidemiology of left ventricular hypertrophy in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Diabetologia* 2005;48:1971-9<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-005-1896-y>.
29. Gupta S, Gupta RK, Kulshrestha M, Chaudhary RR. Evaluation of ECG abnormalities in patients with asymptomatic type 2 diabetes mellitus. *J Clin Diagn Res* 2017;11:OC39-41<https://doi.org/10.7860/JCDR/2017/24882.9740>.
30. Bianco HT, Izar MC, Povoas RM, et al. Left ventricular hypertrophy and QTc dispersion are predictors of long-term mortality in subjects with type 2 diabetes. *Int J Cardiol* 2014;176:1170-2<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2014.07.251>.
31. Dzudie A, Choukem SP, Adam AK, et al. Prevalence and determinants of electrocardiographic abnormalities in sub-Saharan African individuals with type 2 diabetes. *Cardiovasc J Afr* 2012;23:533-7<https://doi.org/10.5830/CVJA-2012-054>.
32. Sellers MB, Divers J, Lu L, et al. Prevalence and determinants of electrocardiographic abnormalities in African Americans with type 2 diabetes. *J Epidemiol Glob Health* 2014;4:289-96<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jegh.2014.04.003>.
33. Okin PM, Devereux RB, Lee ET, Galloway JM, Howard BV, Strong HS. Electrocardiographic repolarization complexity and abnormality predict all-cause and cardiovascular mortality in diabetes: the strong heart study. *Diabetes* 2004;53:434-40.
34. Jimenez-Corona A, Nelson RG, Sievers ML, Knowler WC, Hanson RL, Bennett PH. Electrocardiographic abnormalities predict deaths from cardiovascular disease and ischemic heart disease in Pima Indians with type 2 diabetes. *Am Heart J* 2006;151:1080-6<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ahj.2005.06.033>.
35. van der Heijden AA, Rauh SP, Dekker JM, et al. The Hoorn Diabetes Care System (DCS) cohort. A prospective cohort of persons with type 2 diabetes treated in primary care in the Netherlands. *BMJ Open* 2017;7:e015599<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-015599>.
36. Prineas RJ, Crow RS, Blackburn HW. *The Minnesota code manual of electrocardiographic findings: standards and procedures for measurement and classification*. Boston, Mass.: J. Wright. 1982.
37. Martin SS, Blaha MJ, Elshazly MB, et al. Comparison of a novel method vs the Friedewald equation for estimating low-density lipoprotein cholesterol levels from the standard lipid profile. *JAMA* 2013;310:2061-8<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2013.280532>.
38. Levey AS, Stevens LA. Estimating GFR using the CKD Epidemiology Collaboration (CKD-EPI) creatinine equation: more accurate GFR estimates, lower CKD prevalence estimates, and better risk predictions. *Am J Kidney Dis* 2010;55:622-7<https://doi.org/10.1053/j.ajkd.2010.02.337>.
39. Summary of Recommendation Statements. *Kidney Int Suppl* (2011), vol. 3(1) . 2013: 5-14<https://doi.org/10.1038/kisup.2012.77>.
40. Conroy RM, Pyorala K, Fitzgerald AP, et al. Estimation of ten-year risk of fatal cardiovascular disease in Europe: the SCORE project. *Eur Heart J* 2003;24:987-1003[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0195-668x\(03\)00114-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0195-668x(03)00114-3).
41. Jorstad HT, Boekholdt SM, Wareham NJ, Khaw KT, Peters RJ. The Dutch SCORE-based risk charts seriously underestimate the risk of cardiovascular disease. *Neth Heart J* 2017;25:173-80<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12471-016-0927-2>.
42. Bugger H, Abel ED. Molecular mechanisms of diabetic cardiomyopathy. *Diabetologia* 2014;57:660-71<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-014-3171-6>.
43. Parim B, Sathibabu Uddandhrao VV, Saravanan G. Diabetic cardiomyopathy: molecular mechanisms, detrimental effects of conventional treatment, and beneficial effects of natural therapy. *Heart Fail Rev* 2019;24:279-99<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10741-018-9749-1>.
44. Vinyoles E, Soldevila N, Torras J, Olona N, de la Figuera M. Prognostic value of non-specific ST-T changes and left ventricular hypertrophy electrocardiographic criteria in hypertensive patients: 16-year follow-up results from the MINACOR cohort. *BMC Cardiovasc Disord* 2015;15:24<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12872-015-0012-6>.
45. Lehtonen AO, Puukka P, Varis J, et al. Prevalence and prognosis of ECG abnormalities in normotensive and hypertensive individuals. *J Hypertens* 2016;34:959-66<https://doi.org/10.1097/HJH.0000000000000882>.